

Interaction of *m*-Xylohydroquinone and D-Galactose and D-Glucose

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The reaction of *m*-xylohydroquinone with D-glucose and D-galactose has been studied spectrophotometrically, polarimetrically, and polarographically and the results have been discussed.

The compound *m*-xylohydroquinone, the synthetic active principle of the oil of *Pisum sativum*, has been shown to possess antigonadotropic activity¹. This is believed to be due to the interaction of this compound and the chorionic gonadotropin, as studied *in vitro* by spectrophotometric methods². The chorionic gonadotropin is a protein complex of which two of the constituents are D-galactose and D-glucosamine hydrochloride³⁻⁴. It has been shown earlier⁵ that this hydroquinone in its interaction with the chorionic gonadotropin reacts individually with D-galactose and D-glucosamine, the two constituents of the latter. D-Galactose is a reducing sugar. It was therefore considered worthwhile to probe a little more deeply into the matter to examine how it reacts with D-glucose, which is one of the constituents of the blood fluid. The present communication embodies the results of this investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dilute aqueous solutions of *m*-xylohydroquinone and D-glucose were prepared and absorption curves studied both individually as well as in mixtures of the two with the help of a Beckman spectrophotometer. These data were compared with the absorption curve of water as the solvent blank. Solutions of *m*-xylohydroquinone were prepared with special care to avoid oxidation due to light and atmospheric oxygen. Each solution was therefore charged with nitrogen and preserved away from light.

The concentration of D-glucose used was $2.033 \times 10^{-4}M$ and it was mixed with $1.397 \times 10^{-4}M$ *m*-xylohydroquinone. Concentrations refer to the final concentrations in the mixture. Reference solutions of pure glucose of the same concentration as in the mixture were also examined for comparison. Each result was repeated at least thrice before it was accepted.

1. Sanyal, *Cal. Med. J.*, 1952, 49, 354.
2. Sanyal and Ganguly, *Science & Culture*, 1954, 19, 356.
3. Fieser and Fieser, "Natural Products Related to Phenanthrene", A. C. S. monograph series, 1949.
4. Burrows, "Biological Action of Sex Hormones", Cambridge University Press, 1949.
5. Sanyal *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 830.

Reagents used were all of pure quality and deoxygenated equilibrium water was used throughout. Optical densities, determined with the help of the spectrophotometer, plotted against wave length, at different intervals of time up to about 72 hours have been shown in Fig. 1.

For polarimetric measurements, a similar careful procedure was adopted in preparing solutions. Concentrations of D-glucose and D-galactose used in these measurements were, however, much higher ($0.1457M$ instead of $2.03 \times 10^{-4}M$) because of the inherent difficulty of observation of optical rotation in very dilute solutions. The concentration of *m*-xylohydroquinone was the same as before. Angles of rotation in degrees were measured at different intervals of time both in the pure sugar solution as well as in its mixtures with *m*-xylohydroquinone and comparison was made to detect any chemical change, if possible.

Polarographic studies were conducted in a Cambridge Penwriting Polarograph with solutions of $1.397 \times 10^{-4}M$ *m*-xylohydroquinone and of glucose and galactose, each of the same strength ($2.033 \times 10^{-4}M$). KCl solution ($0.1M$) was used as the supporting electrolyte with a 0.05% solution of gelatin as the suppressor. Measurements were all carried out at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ with the solution kept away from light. Measurements at different sensitivities of the instruments are reported in Table I

TABLE I

Concentration of sugar = $0.147M$.

Time after mixing.	Sensitivity used.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$.	Diffusion current (i_d).
(a) Mixture of <i>m</i> -xylohydroquinone and D-galactose. ($E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and i_d for pure sugar were -1.095 volts and $0.904 \mu A$ respectively).			
$\frac{1}{2}$ hr	1/20	-1.10 volts	$1.40 \mu A$
	1/50	-1.10	1.38
	1/70	-1.10	1.40
24	1/50	-1.10	2.88
	1/70	-1.10	2.80
72	1/70	-1.10	3.85
(b) Mixture of <i>m</i> -xylohydroquinone and D-glucose. ($E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and i_d for pure sugar were -1.1 volts and $1.88 \mu A$ respectively).			
$\frac{1}{2}$	1/30	-1.10	1.88
	1/50	-1.10	1.88
	1/70	-1.10	1.88
24	1/50	-1.10	3.65
	1/70	-1.10	3.63
72	1/70	-1.10	5.61

DISCUSSION

In the absorption curves with glucose, it is obvious that there is the appearance of a new peak at $260m\mu$ (more correctly at $262m\mu$) in addition to the one already present at $290 m\mu$, the latter being attributed to the presence of *m*-xylohydroquinone³. This new peak at $260m\mu$ increases in height and gradually becomes more prominent with the progress

of time. The peak at 290 $m\mu$ simultaneously and gradually loses height. Thus far this observation compares favourably with similar observations with D-galactose⁵.

A study after 24 hours, however, revealed that the peak (Fig. 1) at 260 $m\mu$ was losing its height. The peak at 290 $m\mu$ was simultaneously found to have a tendency to regain its height. This aspect was studied by extending our observations up to 72 hours when the peak at 260 $m\mu$ disappeared completely and that at 290 $m\mu$ regained almost its original height.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

These observations are indicative of an interaction going on between *m*-xylohydroquinone and D-glucose, which progresses with time, probably in a manner similar to that with D-galactose, reported earlier⁵. Evidently, one important point of difference existing in this case is that the compound is most probably not so stable as was the case with D-galactose. The compound appeared to break up gradually with the reformation of *m*-xylohydroquinone and D-glucose, which could be inferred from the gain in height of the peak at 290 $m\mu$ and loss of that at 260 $m\mu$. Further studies reveal that the stability of the complex with D-glucose depends on the concentration of *m*-xylohydroquinone. The lower the amount of this hydroquinone, the less stable is the complex formed, which will be evident from Fig. 2 where the concentration of the hydroquinone is less ($2.18 \times 10^{-3}M$). The whole complex, which formed in the initial stages, completely disappeared in 24 hours, as is evident from the vanishing of the peak at 260 $m\mu$. Unfortunately, the limitations of the apparatus did not permit us to study the effect at concentrations higher than that reported in Fig. 1

A study of mixtures of this hydroquinone with D-galactose, repeated herein, revealed a different picture. There was the appearance of the peak at 260 $m\mu$, as reported earlier⁵,

but the peak had no tendency to vanish although observations were continued for more than 24 hours. The complex formed in this case is therefore more stable. The concentrations of the sugar also indicated to have a similar effect, but it was much less prominent than in the case of the hydroquinone.

For the study of the rates of formation of the complexes with the two sugars, optical density at 260 $m\mu$ was plotted against time. Reaction with D-galactose appeared to be faster than that with D-glucose (Fig. 3).

FIG. 3

Although the absorption studies, mentioned above, revealed the decomposition of the complex and the reappearance of the hydroquinone in course of time, it could not be known from such studies as to what was happening with the sugars used as these sugars did not present any characteristic peak within the UV range studied herein.

Polarimetric studies were therefore resorted to with a view to ascertaining whether there was any decrease in the amount of sugar in consequence of the interaction suggested. Such a study, however, did not prove helpful since the amount of sugars involved in the process was found too small to allow detection of minute changes in concentration; but small changes in the angle of rotation and the observations could not be relied upon, specially in presence of a large excess of unchanged sugar.

Polarographic studies were therefore pursued with these mixtures. Diffusion currents were found to change in the case of mixtures with both the sugars. With pure sugar solutions, none of the diffusion current and the half-wave potential showed any indication of change with time.

It will be evident from the table that the values of the half-wave potentials did not change but remained the same in the mixture as in the pure sugar solution. The diffusion current, on the other hand, almost doubled itself in both the cases in course of 24 hours. With glucose, the amount of increase was greater than that with galactose in 72 hours. Pure *m*-xylohydroquinone was not observed to yield any wave in this region or near about. So the wave, which shows increase in diffusion current with time, must be due to some complex formed, which increases with time.

Spectrophotometric studies show the evidence of the formation of a complex, which is more stable with galactose than with glucose.

Polarographic studies, on the other hand, provides evidence of another type of complex which remains stable and increases in amount even after 72 hours, as indicated by increase in the diffusion current. It suggests that these two types of complexes are rather different. From our previous study with chorionic gonadotropin, it appears that the spectrophotometric studies yield the proper clue; polarographic studies do not present any helpful indication in this case.

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